

Appraisal of Relief Services provided to Emergency Victims: Implications for Reforms in the State Emergency Management Agency Kano, Nigeria

By

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Abstract

This paper appraised relief services provided to emergency victims: implications for reforms in the state emergency management agency Kano, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives focusing on the categories of emergency victims from 2010 to 2019, relief services provided to emergency victims and the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State. The study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State out of which a sample of 390 was selected through the use of purposive and snow-bolling sampling procedure in which From the sample size 30 Officials of KSEMA were selected through Purposive sampling technique and 360 emergency victims were selected through the use of snowball technique. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide and Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA were used in the process of data collection and the two instruments were validated by experts in measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management and reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.84 was obtained. Data was analyzed through the use of descriptive statistics while the data collected through the FGD was analysed through the use of thematic analysis. Findings revealed among others that the immediate needs of the emergency victims are the security of lives and properties, comfortable shelter, essential food stuff, adequate medical facilities, reconstructions, sufficient monetary donations, adequate family welfare, counselling support, relationship building, livelihood activities and spiritual needs to address social, economic and psychological challenges. The study recommended that Government of Kano State should provide a reform on the edict that established the emergency management agency at State levels so as to allow for establishment of emergency management agencies across the 44 local government councils in Kano State. This will properly re-address the issue security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, as well as their family's educational support needs.

Keywords: Emergency victims, Emergency management, Disaster, Reforms and Relief services

Introduction

Contemporarily, emergencies are the results of disasters such as fire outbreaks, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification, and other forms of catastrophe that were eminent of traumatic experiences requiring social and psychological emergency responses in form of providing means to sustain the means for livelihood such as infrastructure, recreational facilities, cultural and traditional festivities, socio-psychological support, and counseling services to the victims of the disasters.

Fire outbreak in Kano State has indeed assumed an alarming proportion as there is barely a day without occurrence of one incidence or the other leaving in its wake destruction of properties worth millions of naira, sometimes loss of lives, devastating impacts on human

lives/livelihoods and infrastructural development (Salkida, 2012, IOM, 2016). Apart from this, within the decade 2010-2019 most of the displaced persons who suffered several attacks of Boko-Haram terrorist have comprised of women, children, the old, and youth migrated in Kano State. In addition to these Kano State has been among the State in Nigeria that witnessed the 2012 flood disaster that drew responses from the public, federal, state and local governments, civil society organizations, and international development partners. These has caused the level in the increase of emergency victims whom were social, morally, and psychologically disturbed and found vulnerable to homelessness, crime, poverty, hunger, and many other social vices. In the urban cities of Kano some of the emergency victims of insurgencies were found wandering the streets engaged in begging. Others who lost their homes and farms were left unemployed, and some of them needed effective counseling service so as to cope with their traumatic experiences. However, in the rural areas most husbands whom were victims of drought run-away from their wives and children living them with no one to take care of them. Emergency victims are therefore in need of assistance that will facilitate them to re-settle back to their homes, religious/cultural engagement, and mental fitness. The social welfare need of these victims needs to be addressed properly by the relief agencies. These needs include housing accommodation, food stuff, medication, counselling and psychotherapeutic sessions, capacity building programmes to restart a new life and many other supportive services that could improve life and living conditions.

Historically, social work is an old helping profession that originated in the 19th century as a result of the emergence of the Industrial Revolution (IR) when there was a great leap in technological and scientific arrangement. This led to frequent migration to urban areas throughout the Western Europe. This led to many social problems, which in turn led to an increase in social activism. However, efforts were made by the then missionaries as an attempt to resolve the problems inherent in the large cities like poverty, prostitution, disease, and many other afflictions. These were undertaken through the provision of medication and vaccines, skill acquisition programmes, westernised agricultural machinisation to improve agricultural production and many other forms of missionary programmes designed to aid vulnerable individuals and communities. While in the United States, workers known as “friendly visitors” were paid by the church and other charitable bodies to work through direct relief, prayer, and evangelism to alleviate the problems. In Europe, chaplains or almoners were appointed to administer the church’s mission to the poor. During this time, rescue societies were initiated to find more appropriate means of self-support for women involved in prostitution. Mental asylums grew to assist in taking care of the mentally ill.

Traditionally, the Extended Family Kinship System (EFS) had contributed immensely to the development of its members and the neighborhood in the history of Nigeria. However, with a high level of increase in individualism and westernization of family values, as a result of nuclearization of life, the EFS could no longer effectively protect the family and the general public in the problematic areas of their existence in the State. Family responsibility has been among the objectives of social welfare since the Elizabethan Poor Laws in 1601, yet the total involvement of government in the welfare system has inadvertently eroded this role of the EFS in our society.

According to Omolewa and Kazeem (1991) “the indigenous society was also a caring one, eager to ensure that no one in the society was deprived of the basic necessities of life”. However, in Nigeria, the formal social work practice opposed the traditional system after the 2nd World War. The pioneer of social work in Nigeria is the Salvation Army and the Green Triangle Group in Lagos. These groups were engaged in assisting the delinquents who have strayed away from the traditional and societal norms of the period. While the Salvation Army established industrial schools where delinquent children are sent for training and readjustment, the Green Triangle established boys and girls club where talents and other useful aspects of the life of the individual delinquents were established and improved (Omolewa and Kazeem 1991).

The contemporary needs of the emergency victims include rehabilitation through active relief service provision in form of programmes such as emergency shelter (Camp), counselling, food items, non-food items, empowerment, vocational skill, infrastructure for restructuring, repatriation, education, monetary assistance, etc (Northeast Nigeria Emergency, 2017). Similarly, the demographics of emergency victims whom are the beneficiaries of relief services from the emergency management agency across states in Nigeria include gender, age, occupations, educational background, etc. Many people in Kano State were among the emergency victims in Nigeria that were vulnerable to various social problems such as homelessness, poverty, displacement, hunger, begging, prostitution, and many other social vices that deteriorated their living standards. Goods worth billions of Naira were provided to various emergency victims by the NEMA in conjunction with SEMA in Nigeria. It is in the light of this that this paper intends to conduct an appraisal of relief services provided to emergency victims and draw its implications for reforms in the state emergency management agency Kano, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The provision of relief services has been considered by social workers as intervention provided to victims of natural and other man-made disasters. The development of the provision of relief as a service was the consequent of the higher increase of emergency victims needing social, economic and psychological assistance so as to reduce vulnerability among them. On January 21, 2012 Kano State started witnessing several Boko-Haram attacks in places like: The Police Headquarters at Bompai; the Zonal Headquarters at Kofar Na'isa and the SSS Headquarters at Badawa. This led to the death of various policemen and innocent people. The convoy of the late Emir of Kano on 19th January, 2013; the Kano Central Mosque on 28th November, 2014, the Farm Centre GSM Market, Sabongari and Kwari Markets; fire out-breaks in places like: Schools, Petrol Stations, Dawanau, Kurmi, Kwari, Sabongari and Farm Centre GSM Market; flooding in Bagwai, Wudil, Minjibir, Kibiya, Bunkure and Kura local government areas: many people lost their lives, some were injured and needed medical assistance, some lost their arms, legs and became crippled and women and children who lost their husbands and fathers became homeless and roamed and participated in begging in the streets in Kano. Various victims were found vulnerable to various social, economic and psychological problems, such as crime, poverty, hunger, hopelessness, frustration, prostitution, unemployment, insecurity and many other social vices that can facilitate the abnormality of victims in Kano State.

The SEMA in Kano State was backed up by an enabling law of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) Act No. 12 of 1999 and as amended by the Act No.50 of 1999 to act as a disaster management structure to formulate and implement policies that enhance the well-being of victims in such emergency situations. Goods worth millions of Naira were provided to various categories of emergency victims. The aim was to enhance the quality of life and improve the well-being of the emergency victims in Kano State. It is in the light of this that the researcher conducted a study to appraise the relief services provided to emergency victims and draw its implications for reforms in the state emergency management agency Kano, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The paper achieved the following objectives:

- i. To examine the categories of emergency victims from 2010 to 2019 provided with by KSEMA. Kano State;
- ii. To determine the relief services provided to emergency victims by SEMA in Kano State, and
- iii. To determine the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State.

Research Questions

The following research question was answered in this study:

- i. What are the categories of emergency victims from 2010 to 2019 in Kano State?
- ii. What are the relief services provided to emergency victims by SEMA in Kano State?
- iii. What are the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State?

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State out of which a sample 390 was selected which consist of up 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims chosen through the use Purposive and snowballing sampling techniques. Two self-developed instruments were used in the collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide and questionnaire named “Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA” (QEVKSEMA). The validity of the instruments was ascertained by experts in measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management and reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method and reliability coefficient level of 0.84 was obtained. Data was analyzed through descriptive statistics and data collected through the FGD was analysed by the use semantics and discussed qualitatively. Frequency (F) and percentage (%), mean (X) as well as cumulative mean score was employed in analyzing questionnaire and decision rule for the acceptance of the statement on items of the questionnaire was obtained by calculating $SA=4, + A=3 + D=2 + SD=1$ which was equal to 10 divided by 4 = 2.5. This means that a cumulative-mean score at or above 2.50 indicated the acceptance of the statement on the items of the questionnaire. As such any cumulative mean score below 2.50 justified statements on the items of the questionnaire were rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019?

From the above illustrations showed the type of emergency conditions faced, the highest degree of 124.56 was covered by the respondents affected by flood in their various communities. These were followed by those (75.6°) who faced fire outbreaks as their emergency condition. Furthermore, those covering a significant degree (18.72) were affected by the other categories of conditions such as armed robbery and hooliganism. However, 57.24° illustrated by this pie chart faced insurgency as their emergency condition. And this was followed by the respondents covering 44.64° as having been faced by community conflict. While those covering 27° were faced by drought, a reasonable degree of (12.6) faced by automobile accidents as their emergency condition requiring the responses of the State

Emergency Management Agency in Kano. The remaining 18° constituted those belonging to other categories that comprised armed robbery and hooliganism.

These were complemented by the FGD conducted with the staff of KSEMA at different periods of time. From the discussion it can be inferred that

“The categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 1010-2019 are victims of fire disaster and victims of flooding”. Other discussant added that “There are also victims of armed robbery and community conflicts.”

However, from FGD it is opined that

“The categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010-2019 are victims of insurgency; victims of community conflict, and victims of drought”. Some of the noted that the categories of emergency victims from the year 2010-2019 are victims of fire disaster and victims of flooding.”

Moreover, the discussant in group C opined that:

The category of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010-2019 are victims of election violence; victims of armed robbery and victims of automobile accident as well as victims of insurgency, victims of fire disaster and victims of flooding were among the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010-2019.

In the light of the above responses, therefore, the respondents at various groups where the FGD was conducted reported that the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019 are victims of fire disaster; flooding; insurgency; community conflicts; drought, election violence, armed robbery, and automobile accidents.

Research Question 2: What is the relief services provided to the different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered during the FGD and it was realized that

The relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims were money and building materials for the victims of fire-outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters and medical facilities for both victims of flood and insurgencies, money and food items.

Some of the group members added that some of the beneficiaries of the relief services at the rural villages benefitted with

“Agricultural facilities for the victims of drought and community conflict; artificial legs/arms, walking-aids and medical facilities for the victims of automobile accidents and insurgencies as well, and money and clothing-materials for the victims of armed robbery.

Research Question 3: What are the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kano State?

Table 1 The immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kano State

Immediate needs	SA		A		D		SD		\bar{X}	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Security of life and property	188	54.2	81	23.3	36	10.4	42	12.1	3.19	Accepted
Comfortable shelter	158	45.5	116	33.4	32	9.2	41	11.8	3.12	Accepted

Essential food stuff	172	49.6	106	30.5	39	11.2	30	8.6	3.21	Accepted
Adequate medical facilities	129	37.2	127	36.6	57	16.4	34	9.8	3.01	Accepted
Reconstruction	87	25.1	145	41.8	65	18.7	50	14.4	2.77	Accepted
Sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare to emergency victims	105	30.3	158	45.5	34	9.8	50	14.4	2.91	Accepted
Counselling support needs to address traumatic experience	73	21.0	176	50.7	65	18.7	33	9.5	2.83	Accepted
Relationship building support needs to address social isolation	81	23.3	177	51.0	53	15.3	36	10.4	2.87	Accepted
Livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges	98	28.2	167	48.1	40	11.5	42	12.1	2.92	Accepted
Spiritual needs to address social life changes	89	25.6	120	34.6	80	23.1	58	16.7	2.69	Accepted

Table 1 shows the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kano State. The security of the life and property of the respondents were strongly agreed by 188 (54.2%) of the sampled. This was followed by 81 (23.3%) who agreed with the said statement on security of life and property. While 42 (12.1%) strongly disagreed, only 36 (10.4%) disagreed with the statement as their immediate need. The mean 3.19 indicated the acceptance of the statement that security of life and property is an immediate need of emergency victims. When the statement on comfortable shelter as an immediate need was stated, 158 (45.5%) strongly agreed with it. This was followed by 116 (33.4%) who opined that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. While a small percentage 9.2 (32) disagreed with the said statement, only 41 (11.8%) strongly disagreed with the statement that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.12 indicated the acceptance that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. However, those who strongly agreed that essential foodstuff was an immediate need of emergency victims constituted 172 (49.6%). This was followed by a reasonable percentage 30.5 (106) who agreed with the said statement. Added to this were 39 (11.2%) who disagreed with the said statement. This was complemented with the remaining 30 (8.6%) who strongly disagreed with the statement on essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.21 indicated the acceptance of the statement that essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims. Regarding the statement that adequate medical facilities was an immediate need of emergency victims, those who strongly agreed and those agreed with the statement were 129 (37.2%) and 127 (36.6%). These were followed by those who disagreed with the said statement 57 (16.4%). The remaining 34 (9.8%) strongly disagreed with that adequate medical facilities were an immediate need of emergency victims. The mean score 3.01 indicated the acceptance of the statement that adequate medical facilities were an immediate need of emergency victims. Furthermore, (148) 41.8% agreed with the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. This was followed by 87 (25.1%) who strongly agreed with said

statement. While (65) 18.7% disagreed, a reasonable percentage 14.4 (50) strongly disagreed as well. The mean score 2.77 indicated the acceptance of the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. Looking in to the table, it is observed that highest percentage 45.5 (158) agreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare were immediate needs of the emergency victims. This was followed by 105 (30.3%) who strongly agreed. While 50 (14.4%) strongly disagreed, only 34 (9.8%) disagreed with the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of the emergency victims. The mean score 2.91 indicated the acceptance of the statement that sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of emergency victims. It has been observed that (176) 50.7% agreed with the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience were an immediate need of emergency victims. This was complemented by (73) 21% who strongly agreed with the said statement. While a sound percentage 18.7 (65) disagreed with the statement, only (33) 9.5% strongly disagreed. The mean score 2.83 indicated the acceptance of the statement that counselling support needs to address traumatic experience was an immediate need of emergency victims. In addition to this were (177) 51% who agreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. This was followed by (81) 23.3% who strongly agreed with the said statement. While a negligible percentage 10.4 (36) strongly disagreed with the said statement, a sound 53 (15.3%) disagreed with the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. The mean score 2.87 indicated the acceptance of the statement that relationship building support needs to address social isolation were immediate need of emergency victims. Moreover, (167) 48.1% agreed with the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims. Only (98) 28.2% strongly agreed with the said statement and - those who disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement were (40) 11.5% and (42) 12.1%. The mean score 2.92 indicated the acceptance of the statement that livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were immediate need of emergency victims. While 89 (25.6%) strongly agreed with the statement that spiritual needs to address social life challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims, the highest percentage 34.6 (120) agreed with the statement, unlike (80) 23.1% who disagreed with the statement and another 58 (16.7%) who also strongly disagreed with it. The mean score 2.69 indicated the acceptance of the statement that spiritual needs to address social life changes was an immediate need of emergency victims.

These statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.95 that is higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of the acceptance of the statements provided in the items of the questionnaire. This implied that the immediate needs of the emergency victims at various levels are money and building materials; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters and medical facilities; and agricultural facilities, artificial legs/arms, walking aids and and clothing materials.

Findings

From the proceeding data analysis, the following findings were deduced:

- i. The categories of the emergency victims in Kano State from the year 2010 to 2019 are victims of fire disaster, flooding, insurgency, community conflicts, drought, election violence, armed robbery and automobile accidents.
- ii. The relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims were money and building materials for the victims of fire outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters and medical facilities for both victims of flood and insurgencies; money, food items, and agricultural facilities for the victims of drought and community conflict; artificial legs/arms, walking aids and medical facilities for the victims of

automobile accidents and insurgencies as well, and money and clothing materials for the victims of armed robbery”.

- iii. The immediate needs of the emergency victims are the security of lives and properties, comfortable shelter, essential food stuff, adequate medical facilities, reconstructions, sufficient monetary donations, adequate family welfare, counselling support, relationship building, livelihood activities and spiritual needs to address social, economic and psychological challenges.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of research question one revealed that the categories of the emergency victims in Kano State from the year 2010 to 2019 are victims of fire disaster; flooding; insurgency; community conflicts; drought; election violence; armed robbery, and automobile accidents. This finding is similar with finding of Obikaeze and Onuoha (2016), Eweka and Olusegun (2016), Agbonkhese, Yerima, Abbaand (2017) which revealed that the categories of emergency victims include among others internally displaced persons, victims of election violence, flooding, drought, fire outbreak, community conflict/clashes, insurgency, armed robbery, drought, desertification, brigandry/hooliganism.

The finding of research question two revealed that the relief services provided to the victims of emergency were money and building materials for the victims of fire-outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters and medical facilities for both victims of flood and insurgencies; money, food items, and agricultural facilities for the victims of drought and community conflict; artificial legs/arms, walking-aids and medical facilities for the victims of automobile accidents and insurgencies as well, and money and clothing-materials for the victims of armed robbery. These findings were similar with that of Aminu and Aujara (2018), thus, food stuff, temporary shelter, vocational skill acquisition, empowerment and educational support services for families.

The last finding of this study revealed that the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kano State are money and building materials for the victims of fire outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters and medical facilities. This finding is related to the findings of the studies conducted by Aminu (2018) that study identified security, housing, accommodation, feeding, medication, clothing, education, empowerment, job and repatriation as the immediate needs of the emergency victims in Kumbotso local government area of Kano State. In addition to this the conducted by Aujara (2018), revealed that the immediate need of the emergency victims are vocational education, civic and citizenship education and entrepreneurial and environmental education. Contrary to this finding was the finding of the study by Silove, Steel and Psychol (2006), which reported that psycho-social needs of victims of disasters are need for mental health interventions, process of reducing acute traumatic stress and chronic posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Conclusion

It was observed that relief services rendered to emergency victims can impact not only on their well-being, but also on improving on their socio-psychological being, hence, humanitarian support services can also arise from counselling perspectives. Also, humanitarian development during crises or disasters comprised of individual and family counselling, vocational support services in form of psycho-counseling service and occupational training that address the traumatic experiences and enhance better adjustment within the societies. This means that there is the need for reform in the relief service provision meant for the improvement of well-being of emergency victims' families, younger children, and neighbourhood that experienced various form of catastrophes requiring other educational programmes in Kano State. And this was based on the fact that there are various emerging global humanitarian support services contemporarily provided by external organizations targeted on the well-being of emergency victims.

Recommendations

from the above conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

- i) Government of Kano State should provide a reform on the edict that established the emergency management agency at State levels so as to allow for establishment of emergency management agencies across the 44 local government councils in Kano State. This will properly re-address the issue security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, as well as their family's educational support needs and
- ii) KSEMA should put hands together with other professional counsellors, Hisbah board and religious faith organizations in the provision of adequate counselling that will reduce the damages and the vulnerability among the emergency victims in Kano State.

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